

Public record of research in progress

“The role of inertia on 2d depinning”

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1 Introduction

The goal is to confirm the predictions of [1] in $d = 2$ dimensions. This document is a public record of research in progress. It lists the current measurements. The main problem is that the system sizes are relatively small in extent and that the statistics are too limited to be conclusive. Please contact the author (tom@geus.me) for any questions or comments, or if you are willing to collaborate.

2 Model

2.1 Dynamics

We consider a model with N particles numbered $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$. Each particle follows Newton dynamics, whereby we use a mass $m = 1$ that is uniform. The degree of freedom is the position u_i such that its dynamics is:

$$m\ddot{u}_i = \underbrace{-\partial_u U_i}_{1) \equiv f_i^p} + \underbrace{\Delta u_i}_{2) \equiv f_i^n} + \underbrace{k_f(\bar{u} - u_i)}_{3) \equiv f_i^f} - \underbrace{\eta \dot{u}_i}_{4) \equiv f_i^d}. \quad (1)$$

Here, $\dot{u}_i \equiv \partial_t u_i$ is the particle’s velocity and $\ddot{u}_i \equiv \partial_t^2 u_i$ is the particle’s acceleration. The restoring force on a particle i is composed of the following terms. 1) Each particle is driven through a potential energy landscape U_i that is piecewise linear elastic with uniform elastic constant $\mu = 1$ and random local barriers, see below. 2) Neighbouring particles interact elastically such that schematically $f_i^n = \Delta u_i$, the Laplacian of u . 3) We drive by connecting each particle with a weak spring of stiffness k_f to a “driving frame” whose position \bar{u} is prescribed. 4) Finally, we add a small damping term with uniform viscosity η to each particle. Underdamped dynamics correspond to $\eta^2 < 4\mu m$. We use $\eta = 0.1$. We study this model numerically by integrating Eq. (1) using the velocity Verlet algorithm. Unless otherwise stated, the parameters (and the disorder) are the same as in [1].

2.2 Interactions

In $d = 2$ we consider a grid of (N_x, N_y) particles such that $N = N_x N_y$. In $d > 1$ we no longer

need high-order elasticity to get a physical roughness. We therefore take:

$$f_i^n = k_2 [u_{m-1,n} + u_{m+1,n} + u_{m,n-1} + u_{m,n+1} - 4u_i] \quad (2)$$

with $k_2 = 1$. The notation is such that $u_{m,n}$ is the position of the particle at location (m, n) , $u_{m-1,n}$ is the position of the particle at location $(m-1, n)$, and so on. Thereby, $m = 1, 2, \dots, N_y$ and $n = 1, 2, \dots, N_x$. To be inserted in Eq. (1) we employ a row-major numbering such that $i = (m-1)N_x + n$. We assume periodicity in both directions such that $u_{m,n} = u_{m+N_y, n+N_x}$ for any m and n . We consider a square grid such that $N_x = N_y = L$.

2.3 Potential energy of interactions

In $d = 2$, the potential energy of interactions expanded to the second order is

$$E = \frac{1}{2} k_2 \varepsilon^2 \quad (3)$$

with

$$\vec{\varepsilon} \equiv \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \vec{e}_x + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \vec{e}_y, \quad \text{and} \quad \varepsilon^2 = \vec{\varepsilon} \cdot \vec{\varepsilon} \quad (4)$$

Consequently, the stress tensor reads

$$\vec{\sigma} = \frac{\partial E}{\partial \vec{\varepsilon}} = k_2 \vec{\varepsilon} \quad (5)$$

The force is then

$$f = \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{\sigma} = k_2 \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{\varepsilon} \quad (6)$$

Here

$$\vec{\nabla} = \vec{e}_x \frac{\partial}{\partial x} + \vec{e}_y \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \quad (7)$$

such that

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{\varepsilon} = \Delta u = \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial y^2} \quad (8)$$

3 Roughness

- We measure the roughness exponent ζ from a simple height-height correlation of the location of the interface u after system spanning events, see Fig. 1. We find $\zeta \simeq 0.74$.
- We check that the structure factor is consistent with this roughness exponent, see Fig. 2. See [1] for the definition of the structure factor.

Figure 1. Correlation of the position of the interface u as a function of distance ℓ , after system spanning events, for different systems of size L (colours). The roughness exponent ζ is fitted on the power law range indicated using a full black line (the dotted black line is the fit's extrapolation).

Figure 2. Structure factor of the interface after system spanning events for different systems of size L (colours). The scaling corresponding to a roughness with exponent ζ is shown using a straight black line (see text).

4 Triggering at f_c

- We define f_c as the lowest force in which we observe a system spanning event in any of our systems (while triggering).
- We test the fractal dimension $S \sim \ell^{d+\zeta}$ in Fig. 3 with the above reported value of ζ .
- We measure the distribution of avalanche sizes $P(S)$ at $f \approx f_c$ in Fig. 4, and find that $\tau \simeq 1.27$. **Open question:** The statistics are too limited to be conclusive on the value of τ . Furthermore, as discussed in [1] a theory is missing.

Figure 3. Measurement of the fractal dimension at $f \approx f_c$: the size S of avalanches as a function of their extent ℓ , with predicted scaling $S \sim \ell^{d+\zeta}$ as a dashed black line. The solid black line shows a direct fit.

Figure 4. Distribution of avalanche sizes, $P(S)$, at $f \approx f_c$. The scaling might approach $P(S) \sim S^{-\tau}$ with $\tau = 1.27$. The inset shows the distributions for different L , the main panel shows the finite size collapse.

5 Triggering at $f > f_c$

- We test our prediction that avalanches are unstable if their linear extent $\ell > \ell_c \sim (f - f_c)^{-\nu}$ with $\nu = 1/(2 - \zeta)$ in Fig. 5 with the above reported value of ζ .
- **Open question:** The statistics are too limited to conclusively support our prediction.

Figure 5. Characterization of the nucleation length ℓ_c beyond which avalanches are unstable, as a function of force f . We define ℓ_c as the upper cut-off of the distribution of avalanche's linear extent: $\ell_c = \langle \ell^3 \rangle / \langle \ell^2 \rangle$ (with $\langle \dots \rangle$ the average over events that are not system spanning, i.e. $\ell < L$). The dotted line shows our prediction.

6 Number of avalanches

- We characterize the activation barriers in Fig. 6.
- We measure the cumulative number of avalanches upon increasing the driving force by Δf after a system spanning event in Fig. 7. Note: we define an avalanche as an event in which at least two particles fail. We find $\theta' \simeq 8.07$.
- Due to the low number of avalanches, the finite system display stick-slip. During loading small avalanches occur (up to a scale l_{\max}) until nucleation of a system spanning event happens once $l_{\max} \sim l_c$. The resulting distribution of event sizes $P(S)$ is bimodal, shown in Fig. 8.

Figure 6. Characterization of (force) barriers after system spanning events. The force needed to trigger failure locally $x_i \equiv \mu(u_i^Y - u_i)$. Plotted is x_{\min} as a function of the number of particles N , which allows fitting the exponent θ of $P(x) \sim x^\theta$ as indicated. x_{\min} is taken as the mean of the minimum of x after n system spanning events. Lower-left inset: $P(x)$ for different system sizes. Upper-right inset: cumulative number of events upon increasing the driving force by Δf after a system spanning event. In both cases, the black line corresponds the θ fitted in the main plot.

Figure 7. Cumulative number of avalanches (whereby at least two particles fail), Φ , upon increasing the driving force by Δf after a system spanning event. This allows fitting of the exponent θ' .

Figure 8. Distribution of the event sizes S of any event (“avalanche” or “system spanning”) during quasistatic loading, for different system sizes as indicated by the colour bar. *Avalanches*, cut-off at a small radius, constitute the majority of events (inset: fraction of events that are avalanches as a function of system size L). *System spanning*, or “slip”, events span the entire system, and constitute the right-hand side peak whose position increases with the system size L .

7 Stick-slip amplitude

- The stick-slip amplitude is defined as the force just before system spanning events (f_s) and just after system spanning events (f_{\min}). It is shown in Fig. 9.
- The inset of Fig. 9 shows our prediction for the stick-slip amplitude with the above reported exponents.
- We measure the relaxation of the force during a system spanning event in Fig. 10.
- **Open question:** These results suggest that $f_c > f_{\min}$ (instead of $f_c \sim f_{\min}$ in [1, 2]). If this is a finite size effect in the definition of f_c remains to be seen if larger systems could be studied.

Figure 9. Main panel: Finite size scaling of the force just before system spanning events (f_s in red) and just after system spanning events (f_{\min} in blue). The markers correspond to the means and the error bars to the standard deviation. Inset: finite size scaling of the stick-slip amplitude $f_s - f_c$ with f_c the smallest force at which a system spanning event was found to occur in any of our finite systems (also shown in the main panel using a dashed black line). The dotted line corresponds to our prediction.

Figure 10. For the largest system. Green curve: relaxation measurement: during a system spanning event the force and velocity are measured. The shown data is the average force per bin of velocity.

References

- [1] Tom W. J. de Geus. The role of inertia on 2d depinning.
- [2] T. W. J. de Geus and Matthieu Wyart. Scaling theory for the statistics of slip at frictional interfaces. *Phys. Rev. E*, 106(6):065001, 2022. ISSN 2470-0045, 2470-0053. doi: [10.1103/PhysRevE.106.065001](https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevE.106.065001). arXiv: [2204.02795](https://arxiv.org/abs/2204.02795).